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D5.4: Report on demonstration at Demosite2: Eilat

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

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Executive summary

Deliverables D5.3, D5.4, D5.5 and D5.6 describe the demonstration activities related to water treatment at the four demonstration sites in Italy, Israel, Spain, and Croatia respectively, performed in task T5.3 “Technological demonstration activities on pilot modules” in WP5 “Demonstration of small loops of water recycling within a complex system”.

Deliverable D5.4 reports the results of the demo activities at Project Ô Demosite 2, carried out in Eilat, Israel, for water reuse in RAS pond and for producing disinfected fresh water for aquaponic produced at IOLR’s facilities. Demo activities involve biological treatment and advanced tertiary treatments. This deliverable stems from the content of D5.2 that describes the details of installation and validation of the SAL.TECH pilot plant for water treatment.

The present report includes:

- an introduction to the demonstration site and to the set of water treatment technologies included in the SAL.TECH water treatment module,
- the purpose of the SAL.TECH modules,
- an overall description of demonstration activities undertaken,
- the results obtained during the demonstration activities.

Table of Contents

Deliverable Development and Review Process	1
Executive summary	2
List of Figures	2
Abbreviations.....	2
1 Introduction	4
2 The SAL.TECH module	8
2.1 Fishponds and Water Loop 1	10
2.2 Denitrification reactor and polishing PBR	13
2.3 Water Loop 2.....	20
3 Testing report	23
3.1 Testing campaign description.....	23
3.2 Water Loop 1.....	24
3.3 Water Loop 2.....	26
4 Conclusions.....	28

List of Figures

<i>Figure 1 Hot deserts climates</i>	5
<i>Figure 2 Max/Min temp (°C) in Eilat</i>	5
<i>Figure 3 Zarchin Desalination plant on the Red Sea. Eilat 30/04/1964</i>	6
<i>Figure 4 IOLR National Institute of Mariculture, Eilat</i>	6
Figure 5 Scheme of SAL.TECH module water loops. N unit: Nitrification unit (ammonia removal); DN unit: Denitrification unit (nitrate removal); Algae Unit: algae photobioreactor (phosphate removal and biomass production for fish feed); Advanced adsorption CNRS: photoactive carbon unit for residual TOC removal and partial disinfection (with UV sources); HINAPEF Iris: high-voltage nanosecond Pulsed Electric Field for disinfection of water and in the mineralization of residual toxic organic pollutants; MD AAU: Membrane Distillation for desalination. Water loop #1 allows the discharge in the sea of low nutrient water and recycling of 20 m ³ /day of purified seawater to fishpond. Water loop #2 allows reuse of 240 litre/day of pure desalinated water in a pilot aquaponic unit.	8

Figure 6 Fish growing system. Stars mark sensors: red for DO, blue for pH, and purple for water level.	10
Figure 7 Control system of the RAS. A) control panel; B) DO and pH sensors in the fish tank; C) backwash apparatus; D) SCADA panel in the local computer.	11
Figure 8 Introduction of new fingerlings	11
Figure 9 Fish biomass (in red) and the monthly amount of fish feed introduced in the RAS. The system started as a smolts production operation. At end of April some smolts were harvested (and transferred to sea net cages), and the remaining smolts were continue	12
Figure 10 Water to fish feed ratio	12
Figure 11 Anoxic activated sludge bioreactor for Denitrification	13
Figure 12 Anoxic activated sludge bioreactor for Denitrification. The reactor includes 2 mixed tanks and a Soliquator (blue unit) for biomass separation	14
Figure 13 Macro-algae production unit. A) harvest and separation unit; B) photobioreactor (PBR)	15
Figure 14 Flocculation test	16
Figure 15 Photobioreactor	17
Figure 16 PBR with growing Algae	17
Figure 17 Sea Urchin feeding on Ulva (Sea Lettuce)	18
Figure 18 Advanced Adsorption module	19
Figure 19 Membrane distillation equipment	21
Figure 20 Aquaponic facility in construction	22
Figure 21 Water quality in the denitrification outlet during 2022	24
Figure 22 Total nitrogen (TN), total ammonium nitrogen (TAN), and soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP) at the outlet of the different treatment units	25
Figure 23 Total Coliforms abatement	26
Figure 24 Permeate conductivity	26
Figure 25 Water salinity after the MD treatment (retentate)	27

Abbreviations

AA: advanced adsorption
AAU: University of Aalborg
BMT: biological mixed treatment
BOD: biological oxygen demand
CFU: colony forming units
CNRS: centre national de la recherche scientifique
DN: denitrification
DO: dissolved oxygen
DOC: Dissolved Organic Carbon
FCR: Feed Conversion Ratio
HiNaPEF: high-voltage nano-second pulsed electric field
IOLR: Israel of Oceanographic and Limnological Research
IRIS: Iris S.r.l.
MBBR: Moving-Bed Biofilm Reactor
MD: membrane distillation
N: nitrification
NCM: National Center for Mariculture
PBR: Photo Bio Reactor
PLC: programmable logic controller
RAS: recirculating aquaculture systems
ROS: reactive oxygen species
SRP: soluble reactive phosphorus
TAN: total ammonium Nitrogen
TN: total Nitrogen
TOC: total organic Carbon
TP: total Phosphorus

TSS: total suspended solids
WWTP: waste water treatment plant

1 Introduction

The main objective of Project Ô is to develop and demonstrate a set of tools enabling circular use of water; among those tools there is a set of innovative technologies for water treatment characterized by high efficiency and low-cost processes, enabling the adoption of a modular approach.

This document collects the activities carried out in Task 5.3 (Technological demonstration activities on pilot modules: running of pilot plants with collection of data for monitoring) regarding Demosite2 in Eilat (Israel). The onsite demonstration and testing campaign was undertaken and resulted in the collection of operative data to evaluate the performance of the SAL.TECH module. A summary of the four demonstration sites is reported below:

Table 1 Brief summary of the four demonstration sites

Demosite 1: Acquedotto Pugliese, Lecce – Italy. Mobile desalination + advanced Oxidation Process for treating contaminated brackish groundwater.
Demosite 2: National Center for Mariculture, Eilat - Israel. Polishing algae plant for water reuse in RAS pond + disinfected fresh water for aquaponic produced through nano-pulsed PEF, membrane distillation and advanced adsorption treatments.
Demosite 3: Almendralejo WWTP, Almendralejo – Spain. Mobile Advanced Adsorption and Photo Fenton with advanced control unit
Demosite 4: Galeb, Omis – Croatia. Photocatalytic module and nanofiltration to allow water reuse in textile industry

The table below summarises key features of Demosite2, technologies and responsibilities for pilot scale module assembly and validation.

Table 2 Summary of the characteristics of Demosite2

Demosite2	Owner: IOLR
SAL.TECH pilot plant	composed by biological mixed treatment (BMT by IOLR); Advanced Adsorption (AA by CNRS); High-voltage nanosecond PEF (HiNaPEF by IRIS); membrane distillation (MD by AAU) and a set of thermal solar panels installed to supply heat through renewable solar energy for MD (Lead: IOLR)
Purpose	Reuse of water from RAS fishpond (Loop1) and high-quality water for aquaponic (Loop2)
Status	installed, validated, and fully operating. Demonstration activities at 50 to 120 m ³ /d for loop1 and 1 to 20 m ³ /d for loop2

Eilat is the southernmost city in Israel and is part of the Southern Negev Desert. In the Köppen climate classification the area is a “hot desert”. In average, the region is characterized by having only 10.5 days of rain (summing to just 24mm) throughout the year. The average temperature (daily mean) is 25.4°C, with hot summers (average high in July is 40.4) and only mild winters (average low is 10.4°C).

Figure 1 Hot deserts climatesⁱ

Figure 2 Max/Min temp (°C) in Eilatⁱⁱ

Eilat was one of the first cities in the world experimenting with water desalination. The first Eilat desalination plant was constructed in the '70s and in 1997ⁱⁱⁱ the first reverse osmosis unit was installed. Since then, Israel developed and applied a multitude of desalination practices on both Red Sea and Mediterranean regions. In Eilat water is a scarce resource: 100% of the tap water is desalinated brackish/sea water.

Figure 3 Zarchin Desalination plant on the Red Sea. Eilat 30/04/1964^{iv}

Figure 4 IOLR National Institute of Mariculture, Eilat^v

The IOLR (Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research) includes three research centres of which the National Center for Mariculture (NCM) will participate in the proposed project. The NCM, which is located in the North Beach of the Gulf of Eilat, is internationally known as a leading research institute in the area of marine aquaculture. Studies carried out at NCM provide the infrastructure for the development of mariculture in Israel as a novel agricultural branch utilizing marine and brackish water and for the establishment of associated biotechnological industries. The NCM is made up of nine research groups

working interactively to domesticate marine fish and other marine species having a high economic value for aquaculture.

The main research areas include fish reproduction, larval rearing and physiology, pathology, algal and zooplankton culture, genetic improvement of farmed marine species, development of feeds, research, and development of cost effective and environmentally friendly systems for intensive fish growth as well as integrated systems for growth of fish, shellfish, and algae.

The professional staff at the IOLR in Eilat includes about 40 scientists, research assistants and technicians. The research infrastructure provides a continuous supply of filtered and UV treated seawater to a wide array of experimental and semi-commercial rearing tanks and ponds. In addition, the Eilat facility has a number of well-equipped analytical laboratories carrying out molecular, biochemical and biological research.

In this context operates the RAS: recirculating aquaculture system. In recent years, NCM devoted a substantial amount of its efforts in the development of the Eilat RAS, a land-based aquaculture plant for fish rearing in seawater ponds.

The technology of recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) realizes environmentally friendly strategies for reducing ecological footprints, and enables an efficient use of energy, land and water resources. Routinely, in RAS culture systems a percentage of the water is passed from the outflow back through the fish growing system following treatment and removal of wastes, mostly nitrogenous substances resulting from protein metabolism. The RAS utilizes biofilters for ammonia oxidation, since ammonia is highly toxic to fish. The resulting nitrate is less toxic and can accumulate in the fish growing system up to relatively high concentrations, allowing to reduce the rate of external water exchange. However, this treatment is insufficient since environmental regulations are now imposing stringent water quality standards, including nitrate removal from RAS farming effluent.

Through the adoption of technologies developed under the flag of Project Ô, the plant recirculates most of the water needed for the fish rearing, thus requiring a minimal replenishing of the ponds from the Red Sea. The potentially negative impacting waste of these ponds (such as nitrates, phosphates, and ammonia) are handled not only avoiding their direct discharge in the Red Sea, but they're also used by other module's technologies to produce fish feed and micronutrients in a concrete circular economy perspective.

2 The SAL.TECH module

WP5 is directed to show the tools that allow water management in small loops, in terms of advanced technologies and impact evaluation tools: this also includes the demonstration activities reported in this deliverable. Whilst D5.2 reported the site preparation, the installation of the pilot plants and their operation, this document instead focuses on the demonstration activities and data collection at Demosite2.

The layout of SAL.TECH module at Demosite2 is described in detail in D5.2; the summary of the water loops is reported below. The purpose of the module is to recycle the sea water of the fishponds, to avoid drawing water from Red Sea and discharge nutrients and to reuse water in aquaponic system after TOC and microbial abatement and desalination.

Figure 5 Scheme of SAL.TECH module water loops. N unit: Nitrification unit (ammonia removal); DN unit: Denitrification unit (nitrate removal); Algae Unit: algae photobioreactor (phosphate removal and biomass production for fish feed); Advanced adsorption CNRS: photoactive carbon unit for residual TOC removal and partial disinfection (with UV sources); HINAPEF Iris: high-voltage nanosecond Pulsed Electric Field for disinfection of water and in the mineralization of residual toxic organic pollutants; MD AAU: Membrane Distillation for desalination. Water loop #1 allows the discharge in the sea of low nutrient water and recycling of 20 m³/day of purified seawater to fishpond. Water loop #2 allows reuse of 240 litre/day of pure desalinated water in a pilot aquaponic unit.

Key characteristics of input water are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3 Main characteristics of RAS water designed vs. measured average values (after nitrification reactor) – Demosite2

Parameter	Units	RAS Process Water Quality	
		Design Values	Averaged Results
Temperature	°C	23.0	23.4 ± 1.0
Salinity	ppt	40	40
Dissolved oxygen (DO)	mg/l; [%]	6.8; [>80%]	9.6 ± 0.5; [>80%]
pH		7.0	6.87 ± 0.1
Alkalinity	meq/L	1.5	1.44 ± 0.15
CO2	mg/l	<8.0	8.4 ± 0.16
TAN	mg/l	2.0-2.5	2.3 ± 0.17
NO2-N	mg/l	0.5	0.47 ± 0.24
NO3-N	mg/l	15-20	15.9 ± 0.75
TSS	mg/l	10.0-15.0	10.0-15.0
P-PO4	mg/l	2.0	2.1

Table 4 Current environmental regulations issued by the Israeli Ministry of environment

Parameter	Units	Concentration Limits		Annual Load Limits ton/year
		Averaged	Maximum	
BOD	mg/l	10	15	3.3
TSS	mg/l	20	30	
Turbidity	NTU	5	8	3.3
pH		6.5 < pH < 9.0	6.5 < pH < 9.0	
NH4-N	mg/l	3	5	
NO3-N	mg/l			
TAN	mg/l	5	10	0.93
Total P	mg/l	2	3	0.39

The demonstration activities took place in EILAT, at IOLR facilities. The first part of demonstration activities involved the optimization of process parameters to achieve the best treatment.

Demonstration activities for water Loop1 started more than one year before the other demonstration activities, already in WP2, since it was more convenient to implement the BMT treatment directly at pilot scale, skipping the bench scale stage.

2.1 Fishponds and Water Loop 1

The fish production system is based on the recirculating aquaculture system (RAS). These are land-based fish-growing systems where the fishes are reared in a tank and the water goes through a set of treatment units to enable the reuse of water in the rearing tank. The RAS in this study consists of 2 separate fish tanks, 60m³ each, where water is continuously recirculated. Part of the water from these tanks is leaked to the water treatment via a side stream (Figure 6). The water treatment includes:

- suspended solid removal by a packed bed solid filter
- a moving bed bioreactor MBBR for nitrification (where the ammonia secreted from the fishes is converted into nitrites and nitrates)
- an air flotation separator for dissolved protein and fine suspended particle removal.

Figure 6 Fish growing system. Stars mark sensors: red for DO, blue for pH, and purple for water level.

A control system based on Allen-Bradley PLC, operates the RAS in a semi-automated mode Figure 7 Diffusers opening and washing (mainly of salt precipitation), solid-filter backwash, water circulation flow,

aeration, and emergency oxygen are controlled. In addition, alarms, local and online SCADA, and data-logging are included.

Figure 7 Control system of the RAS. A) control panel; B) DO and pH sensors in the fish tank; C) backwash apparatus; D) SCADA panel in the local computer.

To prepare the RAS for the experimental run, the system was disinfected using chlorine for 5 days; then, 40,000 Sea Bream fingerlings (average weight of 10 g) were introduced into the RAS.

Figure 8 Introduction of new fingerlings

The fish arrived from a nearby hatchery farm (ARDAG). As a result of the disinfection, the microbial community in the biofilter (nitrification unit) was removed and the nitrification was not operating. Hence, in order to maintain ammonia concentration at a non-toxic level, low feeding ration was used, leading to a relatively high-water exchange ratio (as can be observed in Figure 9). The biofilter acclimatization was slower than expected, most probably due to low temperature. After 5 months of operation, the biofilter activity was stabilized and the feeding rate was optimal. Once the nitrification reactor settled, the average recirculation rate was over 3000 m³/day with a heavy dependence on fish's biomass and fishes' feed.

During the last month about 80 kg fish feed (45% protein) introduce daily into the RAS, and fish present very fast and efficient growth (**FCR** of 1.2).

Figure 9 Fish biomass (in red) and the monthly amount of fish feed introduced in the RAS. The system started as a smolts production operation. At end of April some smolts were harvested (and transferred to sea net cages), and the remaining smolts were continue

Figure 10 Water to fish feed ratio

2.2 Denitrification reactor and polishing PBR

Part of the water recirculating through the RAS is leaked towards the denitrification unit (at an average rate of 144m³/day). The denitrification system (Figure 12) is based on a single-pass anoxic activated sludge bioreactor. It is composed of:

- two 34 m³ round tanks equipped with an overhead mixer (60-120 RPM)
- a Soliquator for solid separation
- two sand filters.

While most of the water is discharged to the sea (about 120m³/day), a side stream with an average flow rate of 20 m³/day is conveyed to the macroalgae tanks. The tanks are used as a polishing stage and recover nutrients (Nitrogen and Phosphorous) before discharge. This operation is essential to comply with the Israeli legislation (discharge to sea). The PBR (PhotoBioReactor) consists of two 40 m³ square fiberglass tanks. Mixing and gas exchange (CO₂ supply and oxygen stripping) is based on aeration, which is embedded within the tank floor. The Algae outlet in the bottom is connected to the designated unit for macroalgae harvest and separation. The harvested Algae can be used to feed other species (see for example Figure 17) as sea urchin.

Figure 11 Anoxic activated sludge bioreactor for Denitrification

Figure 12 Anoxic activated sludge bioreactor for Denitrification. The reactor includes 2 mixed tanks and a Soliquator (blue unit) for biomass separation

Figure 13 Macro-algae production unit. A) harvest and separation unit; B) photobioreactor (PBR)

During the operation of the denitrification reactor, after the stabilization of the microbial community, a flocculation test was performed (Figure 14)

This test was in collaboration with the flocculants producer (Nalco). Twelve polymers, including anionic, cationic, and non-ionic were tested, all Grass approved and food grade. For the most effective polymer (Nalco71300.11R), an optimal dose was characterized (20 ppm).

Figure 14 Flocculation test

The combination of nitrification and denitrification units allows for the reduction of N-NO_3^- and TAN to one third, complying with the Israeli environmental regulations (Table 4 Current environmental regulations issued by the Israeli Ministry of environment) and allowing a reduction of the input water withdrawn from the Red Sea (Flow1 in Table 5) to an average of 164 m³/day, with a mean recirculation of over 3000 m³/day into the fish pond.

The algae photobioreactor (Figure 15 and Figure 16) delivers water in which nutrients strictly linked to eutrophication (nitrates, phosphate, ammonia) are abated (see Figure 22). Total Nitrogen and Total Phosphorus are reduced by a factor of (at least) 2. Dissolved organic carbon (DOC) levels are around 4-6 mg/L in the photobioreactor effluent. Moreover, from each PBR tank, it's expected a biomass production up to 160 kg (wet weight) per week (Ulva in Figure 17 and Gracilaria are the species of algae in production). It is used in the aquaculture for sea urchin feeding and as an ingredient in grey mullet feed but could be even used for human consumption. The production of 160kg/week of algae equates (once dried) to 40kg/week of fish feed production.

Figure 15 Photobioreactor

Figure 16 PBR with growing Algae

Figure 17 Sea Urchin feeding on Ulva (Sea Lettuce)

The Advanced Adsorption (Figure 18) unit uses absorption on activated charcoal to abate residual organic and inorganic compounds. Water from the algae PBR is rich in organic compounds that can be dangerous to both the membrane distillation unit and to the fishponds. The organic load expressed as DOC (see Table 5) is abated with efficacy by the Advanced adsorption treatment (>75% of abatement). The activated charcoal used in the module is prone to saturation with time (intrinsic characteristic to every adsorption media). The unit comes equipped with UV illumination, integrated in the unit to perform chemical photolysis of the absorbate, thus regenerating the absorbent. Both TN and TP have abatement levels comparable to DOC abatement (75%).

Figure 18 Advanced Adsorption module

2.3 Water Loop 2

The combination of pulsed electric field technology (HiNaPEF) and membrane distillation (MD) allows to obtain chemically and microbiologically pure water for use in the aquaponic system.

Water from the Algae plant can be microbiologically contaminated with bacteria (see for example the 10th month in Figure 21). The HiNaPEF treatment can inactivate this microbial charge using pulsed electric fields. The HiNaPEF generator has been developed to deliver short current pulses (in the nanosecond range) to perform this microbiological decontamination. The electrical discharges from the generator act on the cell membranes, rendering them either reversibly or irreversibly permeable. This leads to inactivation (or even death) of the microbial cells. The unit comes equipped with a reactor, with optimized geometry, that distributes the electric field evenly inside its volume. The high voltages that is present on the reactor's plates during the electric pulses, generate the so-called reactive oxygen species (ROS, mainly ozone and OH radicals) which further improve the microbiological decontamination and are also extremely reactive with potentially harmful chemical species that can be present in the water. This treatment is also propaedeutic to avoid membrane fouling of the Membrane Distillation unit that is fed from it.

The membrane distillation unit equipment installed in Eilat is used to produce very high purity water for the aquaponic plant. Since it's already been extensively described in previous documents we'll proceed with a brief summary of its operation.

The driving force of the process is the thermal gradient that is present between the two sides of a porous, hydrophobic membrane. The pores of this membrane are large compared to water molecules (0.1 to 1 micron) but not “wetable” thanks to membrane’s hydrophobicity. Liquid water has high surface tension, hence it’s not able to permeate across the membrane. Conversely, water vapour easily permeates the membrane, leading to a very high purity water output. A key aspect of the membrane distillation unit installed in Eilat is that feed water is heated by thermal solar panels, which in turns leads to reduced electrical energy requirements. Being fed with salty water (with essentially the same salinity of the Red

Sea) the retentate of MD is a brine (around 200 g/L of salts). From this brine, micronutrients can be crystallized and reused for further processes in the SALTECH module.

Figure 19 Membrane distillation equipment

Figure 20 Aquaponic facility in construction

An aquaponic plant is installed (Figure 20) at the end of Loop 2. This plant is fed with the high purity water decontaminated by the HiNaPEF and MD operation. The greenhouse facility in Eilat can be observed in Figure 20.

3 Testing report

3.1 Testing campaign description

The testing campaign was set-up to establish if the SAL.TECH module is correctly operating:

- in relation to the specification drawn in D5.1
- in relation to the current Israeli legislation on water quality

In D5.2 we described the installation and the validation procedures of the SAL.TECH module. Here we'll describe the subsequent testing campaign.

Since operations of Loop 1 and Loop 2 began on different dates and being intrinsically characterized by their own variability, two different testing campaigns were set up with optimal sampling frequency for the processes involved. Sampling, handling, and storage was conducted in line with the prescription from D2.1.

3.2 Water Loop 1

Regarding Water-Loop1, the effluents of the denitrification were sampled once a week during the first stage of operation. After integration of the flocculation into the denitrification operation, the effluents were sampled 3 days a week, 3 times during the day (morning, noon, and afternoon). Water quality in the 10 months of operation can be evaluated in Figure 21.

Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.

Figure 21 Water quality in the denitrification outlet during 2022

Similarly, to the RAS operation, the nitrification reactor required a stabilization time that was around 5 months. This is highly notable evaluating the TSS and TP values. During the operation, a decline in pH was observed. This is most probably due to an increase in organic load and nitrogen to the reactor (RAS effluents), resulting in enhanced CO₂ production during denitrification. Interestingly, a high number of enterococcus (ETC) colonies was detected in the denitrification. Some colonies were sent for sequencing and identification. It was found to be *Citrobacter freundii*, a facultative anaerobic gram-negative bacterium of the family Enterobacteriaceae.

Data from the last 3 months (SEP- NOV) of operation, including flocculation system, is presented in Figure 22. Based on the differences between measured TN concentration and expected TN concentration in the RAS effluent, it was found that about 50% of nitrogen excreted by fishes was removed in the RAS through

passive denitrification. These phenomena occur because of poor solid evacuation in the fish tank and low frequency of solid filter backwash. It should be noted that accumulation of solids in the rearing unit is correlated with an increased potential of disease outbreaks and an increased oxygen demand (BOD).

Significant removal of TN was observed in the solid separation unit (soliquator), suggesting accumulation of nitrogen in the biomass (suspended matter). As expected, no accumulation of ammonia nitrogen (evaluable from TAN) was detected in the denitrification system. Two mechanisms can explain it:

- Some activity of Anammox bacteria, which is correlated to fish's feces.
- The assimilation and/or absorption of ammonia into the biomass. It is also supported by the removal of TN by solid separation. Maybe this process was enhanced due to the use of flocculant.

Most of SRP (soluble reactive phosphorus) removal was observed in the mix tank. This is a result of assimilation of phosphates into the biomass. Macro-algae effluent shows low concentration of all nutrients measured.

Figure 22 Total nitrogen (TN), total ammonium nitrogen (TAN), and soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP) at the outlet of the different treatment units.

3.3 Water Loop 2

Water from loop 2 was sampled once a week for the entire testing campaign. Here we report the data from the campaign for the technologies inside loop 2.

HiNaPEF has proven reliable in controlling microbiological contamination. In Figure 23 we report the abatement levels relative to the total coliforms count (CFU). The average abatement is 94.8%.

Figure 23 Total Coliforms abatement

The membrane distillation unit operated in line with the expected performance (from D2.3), producing 240l/day of distilled water that can be used for the aquaponic plant. Relevant parameters are shown in Figure 24 and Figure 25.

Figure 24 Permeate conductivity

Figure 25 Water salinity after the MD treatment (retentate).

4 Conclusions

Here we report in Table 5 a summary of the relevant parameters for the SALTECH module.

Table 5 Water quality parameters of the flows in water loop #1 and water loop#2 - average values over the entire demonstration period¹

flow #		flow rate (m ³ /d)		salinity (ppt)		TN (mgN/L)		TP (mgP/L)		TOC (mgC/L)		DOC (mgC/L)	
1	input Red Sea	164	± 37	39.6	± 1	0.8	± 0.14	0.01	± 0.002	2.36	± 0.4	2.30	± 0.4
2	fishpond outlet	3360	± 2400	39.7	± 1	7.20	± 4.0	0.52	± 0.05	3.41	± 0.5	3.40	± 0.5
3	recycled nitrification outlet	3196	± 2300	39.8	± 1	8.00	± 4.0	0.47	± 0.05	3.30	± 0.5	3.10	± 0.5
2bis	denitrification input	164	± 37	39.8	± 1	8.00	± 4.0	0.47	± 0.05	3.30	± 0.5	3.10	± 0.5
discharge to sea	denitrification output ²	142	± 32	40.4	± 1	4.4	± 1.4	0.08	± 0.01	3.00	± 0.5	2.90	± 0.5
4	algae unit inlet	22	± 2	40.4	± 1	4.4	± 1.4	0.08	± 0.01	3.00	± 0.5	2.90	± 0.5
6	algae unit outlet	22	± 2	40.8	± 1	2.4	± 0.02	0.02	± 0.01	6.30	± 1.1	6.20	± 1.1
8	AA outlet recycled to fish pond2	22	± 2	40.8	± 1	0.72	± 0.02	0.006	± 0.001	1.00	± 0.02	1.00	± 0.02
input to Loop2	from AA outlet	0.3	± 0.03	40.8	± 1	0.72	± 0.02	0.006	± 0.001	1.00	± 0.02	1.00	± 0.02
	HiNaPEF outlet	0.3	± 0.03	40.8	± 1	0.72	± 0.02	0.006	± 0.001	0.95	± 0.02	0.93	± 0.02
	Permeate	0.24	± 0.03	3*10 ⁻³	± 1*10 ⁻³	2*10 ⁻³	± 0.005	1.0*10 ⁻⁴	± 1*10 ⁻⁴	0.025	± 0.001	0.03	± 0.001
	Brine	0.06	± 0.003	209.0	± 20	3.6	± 0.01	0.03	± 0.02	4.75	± 0.5	4.65	± 0.5

The SALTECH module is the most complex of the modules developed under the flag of Project Ô. It proved to be able to cope with the challenges characterizing a mariculture plant feeding from the Red Sea. The water recirculation rate achieved for the fishponds is high, enabling to reduce the amount of water required from the Red Sea. One of the objectives of Furthermore Loop 1 (N unit, DN unit, Algae PBRs and AA) greatly reduces the potential eutrophication impact of the fishponds (a thorough analysis is available in D6.6). The water discharged to the Red Sea comply with the Israeli legislation (see Table 4 for reference).

As for Loop 2, HiNaPEF proved his efficacy in controlling microbial charge (see Figure 23). Membrane Distillation provides water suitable for aquaponics with a limited (and mostly renewable) energy input. In this demonstration site, the project Ô objective QO1 is achieved, pertaining the 30% reduction of the Water Footprint.

¹ The uncertainties specified are related to the variability of the samples throughout the testing campaign, which are orders of magnitude higher than the uncertainties related to the instrumentation or to the analytical techniques utilized for their determination.

² The denitrification output comprises also flocculation and sand filtering.

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- ⁱ Beck, H.E., Zimmermann, N. E., McVicar, T. R., Vergopolan, N., Berg, A., & Wood, E. F. - "Present and future Köppen-Geiger climate classification maps at 1-km resolution".
- ⁱⁱ <https://weather-and-climate.com/average-monthly-Rainfall-Temperature-Sunshine,Eilat,Israel>
- ⁱⁱⁱ Water Desalination Report, Volume 33, 1997, Issue 25
- ^{iv} Moshe Pridan (Israel National Photo Collection)
- ^v http://www.naf-iolr.org/?page_id=211